

ADVANTAGES OF DISTANCE LEARNING IN IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING SYSTEM

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Abstract. This article examines the rapidly entering the education system of distance learning and its advantages in improving the professional development system. Distance learning is defined as a pedagogical process carried out on the basis of information technologies and telecommunications, through virtual classrooms and resources.

Keywords: professional development system, distance learning (training), information and communication technologies (ICT), virtual training center, professional competence, Internet, teacher retraining, electronic educational materials.

Distance learning is rapidly entering the world education system as a separate form of education, and is being introduced as interactive education. Distance learning is a pedagogical process based on information technologies and telecommunications.

Distance education is carried out through educational resource centers, the Internet, and postal communications. Distance education is mainly provided through virtual slides, and if a student enters a virtual classroom through a portal, he has the opportunity to participate in the process.

Distance education is a process of transferring and mastering knowledge, skills, abilities, and methods of acquiring them, based on indirect contact between participants who are far from each other, in a special psychological-pedagogical and information and communication technology environment.

Distance education directs a person to self-development, to become a necessary specialist in the future. Determining the model for implementing distance education is important from the point of view of strategic planning; the preparation of educational, methodological, educational and didactic materials for distance education, their optimization, systematization, design, as well as the organization of the educational process are carried out on the basis of previously selected model projects.

A system of distance retraining and advanced training of teachers has been established in our republic.

The Center for the Development of Distance Education and its regional centers are directly engaged in distance retraining and advanced training of teachers in their respective regions.

Distance training involves teachers receiving the necessary educational, teaching and methodological materials from the Internet or directly from these centers (such materials may be recorded on audio, video media, as well as computer disks), and, having a computer and the Internet at home, independently working on themselves and improving their skills in their subject area, using the available opportunities, at the school where they work, in a cluster school near their place of residence, or directly at these centers.

Distance learning is a virtual learning process lasting 3 months.

Distance learning:

- improving skills without leaving work;
- significantly reducing costs;
- using the latest advances in information and telecommunications technologies during the learning process and thereby accessing and understanding the global information space;
- choosing a convenient time to learn the material;
- engaging in the teacher's work at a time and place convenient for him, at a pace that is convenient and appropriate for him;
- is important for its advantages such as equality of conditions and opportunities for everyone, regardless of health and socio-economic background.

The student is required to have a higher education, a certain level of computer literacy, as well as the skills to exchange information in local and global communication networks.

The priority areas for the formation and development of an information support complex for a virtual educational center based on an educational Web server should be determined by the nature of the activities of the virtual educational center, the information structure of which is located on the server of the educational institution and provides information support for the administrative, educational-methodical, scientific-research activities of the virtual educational center. This can be both distance learning and the implementation of creative projects. The teacher can plan the procedure for using information resources, consider the management of the educational or creative process and the organization of monitoring. Of course, the creation of such sites can be practically implemented step-by-step, using bottom-up technology - from simple registration of students to full administrative management of the entire activities of the virtual educational center.

The content of the educational server is represented by the preparation of various electronic educational materials. The main role in this, of course, belongs to teachers, but a wide field of activity opens up for students. This may include, for example, the preparation of Web pages containing review materials, annotated catalogs with lists of the most valuable information sources (Internet links) in a particular discipline, the formation of databases in modeling programs. Their capabilities for organizing the educational process are being studied. However, unfortunately, a single standard for such software has not yet been developed. Educational institutions and centers (in our country and abroad) implementing distance and open learning programs are developing their own software, taking into account the specifics of their activities, in order to maintain the information environment.

In addition, means of organizing the use of educational and methodological materials and working with them via a local network and the Internet; organization and implementation of the transmission of educational (training) programs, textbooks, assignments via networks are included.

Distance learning courses have been introduced in mathematics, computer science, physics, chemistry, biology, geography, fundamentals of economic knowledge, English, German, French, native language and literature, and primary education subjects, using the latest, modern methods, and using new information and communication technologies in teaching. In short, distance learning is of great importance in improving the system of advanced training, ensuring the continuity of teachers' professional competence, and introducing modern education.

References:

1. Otabaev A.K. "Regulatory and Legal Acts in the Field of Information and Communication Technologies in Ensuring State Security" // In Volume 61 (2025) of Miasto Przyszłości Kielce, Impact Factor: 9.9. ISSN-I: 2544-980X).
2. ЗҚ Музаффаров // Олий ҳарбий таълим муассасалари курсантлари ва тингловчиларининг ватанпарварлик даражасини баҳолаш мезонлари. Volume 48 (2024) of Gospodarka i Innowacje (2545 0573). С. 584-587. 2024/6/17.
3. Rustam M. Khalilov // "Risks and threats to the states' military security in the 1st half of the XXI century". In Volume 54 (2024) of Miasto Przyszłości. Impact Factor: 9.9. SJIF 2023: 6.567.
4. Otabaev A.K. The role of social partnership in community life. Web of Technology: Multidimensional Research Journal (IFSIJ JIF 7.425, ISSN (E) 2938-3757). Volume 1, Issue 9, Decembr, 2023.
5. Otabaev A.K. Political and legal foundations of civil society development. Diversity Research: Journal of Analysis and Trends (ISSN (E): 2810-6393, IFSIJ JIF 7.665).Volume 01, Issue 09, December 2023.
6. Otabayev A.K. "Relationships Between Military Service and Religion" // In Volume 54 (2024) of Miasto Przyszłości, Impact Factor: 9.9. SJIF 2023: 6.567.